

APPLICATION OF SURGICAL PRACTICE ORGAN-PRESERVING RECONSTRUCTIVE SURGERY SEVERE PROLAPSE OF THE FEMALE GENITAL ORGANS.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10997267>

Purpose of the study: to determine the immediate and long-term results after treatment and surgical practice for grade III-IV genital prolapse in women of reproductive age.

Research method and material. Under our supervision were 48 patients who came to us with severe genital prolapse at the age of 25-39 years. The patients were familiarized with all examination methods, their anamnesis, general clinical and laboratory tests, the degree of genital prolapse, ultrasound examination of the pelvic organs, additional complications, colposcopy, bacteriological and bacterioscopic examination of vaginal smears were performed. In addition, the types and volume of primary surgical interventions performed, the course of the postoperative period, and the observed complications were carefully studied and analyzed.

Results of the study and their discussion: The results obtained show that the 24 patients we examined were diagnosed with level III-IV genital prolapse according to the POP-Q classification. The age of patients is 34-41 years. At the clinic, 11 (45.9%) of our patients complained mainly of discomfort in the vagina, dyspareunia and dysfunction of the genitals, and the remaining 13 (54.1%) had severe complications of the disease: urinary incontinence, gas incontinence, cystocele, complications of rectocele observable. When studying the obstetric anamnesis of the patients, it was found that almost 19 (79%) of our patients experienced late delivery complications. In 9 patients with fetal macrosomia, injuries to the cavity and vagina were performed, in 4 patients an episiotomy was performed, and in 6 patients there was a history of cervical rupture during childbirth with breech presentation. In connection with the above complications and complaints, patients with severe prolapse underwent limb-sparing surgery.

Conclusion: Analysis of modern literature shows this. Genital prolapse in women of reproductive age is considered a pressing problem in gynecology. It should be noted that more than 35% of patients with recurrent genital prolapse undergo repeated surgery. The advantage of the operation is that patients get up the next day. It is allowed to sit and walk for 3-4 days. On the 7th day, patients

will be given an answer. The effectiveness of treatment was assessed in 3 stages, after 3, 6 months and 1 year, as well as the quality of life of women. Before surgery, 100% of women rated their quality of life as poor, and 1 year after surgery, 40% of them rated it as "bad" and 60% as "good." Complications observed with genital prolapse are reduced by 89%. It should be noted that no recurrence of genital prolapse was observed within 3 years after the operation.

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ВЛАГАЛИЩА. Журнал вестник врача, 1(2), 100–103.
<https://doi.org/10.38095/2181-466X-2020942-99-102>

